

Mild processing innovations to preserve fresh fruits and vegetables (FOX/Shealthy)

10:30 - 12:35 Wednesday, 3rd November, 2021

Room 1A

Presentation type Orals

Simona Mincione, Kerstin Pasch

This session will give insights and present the latest results of the two European projects FOX (Innovative down-scaled food processing in a box) and SHEALTHY (Non-Thermal physical technologies to preserve fresh and minimally processed fruit and vegetables). Both projects are funded by Horizon2020 under the 'SFS-16-2018 - Towards healthier and sustainable food'. Next to innovative technical solutions, FOX and SHEALTHY have a specific look at new business opportunities for farmers and small-medium sized enterprises, consumer engagement and sustainability aspects. The projects are 'Research and Innovation Activities' and started in parallel in 2019 and will run until 2023.

For more information visit www.fox-foodprocessinginabox.eu

10:30 10:55 - **At a glance: FOX and SHEALTHY**, Kerstin Pasch, Simona Mincione

10:55 11:15 - **Mobile solutions for fruit and vegetables producers**

11:15 11:35 - **Sustainable futures in the food sector - a methodological combination of future scenarios and LCA**

11:35 11:55 - **Application of non-thermal processing to minimally processed F&V based products.**

11:55 12:15 - **Consumer- and Business- led Innovation**

12:15 12:35 - **Discussion: Hurdles about implementing ideas?** , Kemal Aganovic, Moderator, Schlüter, Oliver Moderator

10:30 - 12:35

S04 Mild processing innovations to preserve fresh fruits and vegetables

Symposia Session organizer information

Jeroen Knol

Speakers/Presenters details

Kerstin Pasch

Simona Mincione

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S04.1 At a glance: FOX and SHEALTHY

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Abstract

The FOX project: The fruit and vegetable sector in Europe needs innovative and flexible technologies for processing. The EU-funded FOX project focuses on mobile and flexible processing units for small and medium-size companies and farmers that wants to apply advanced technology applications. The project concentrates on mild processing technologies: from preservation to packaging and quick quality control for healthier food production. It will be deployed in six EU regions with considerable fruit and vegetable

production and will evaluate new business opportunities. In addition, it will estimate its environmental, social, business and health impacts. The promotion of the project's method, as well as the debate concerning policy recommendations, will be promoted by a European Interest Group of small-scale food processors.

The SHEALTHY project focus on the development of a combination of non-thermal sanitization, preservation and stabilization methods to preserve quality and improve shelf life of minimally processed fruits and vegetables products. The combined and optimised mild technologies will be demonstrated and validated in 2 business cases: Minimally processed fruits and vegetables and Fruit and vegetable-based juices & smoothies. The project will significantly advance the knowledge towards minimal processing technologies, demonstrating in an industry-relevant environment (11 pilot trials) combining 10 different mild technologies. Sustainable and flexible processing methods will be transferred and adapted to the need of local F&V micro and SMEs, interconnecting primary producers through novel cooperative business models and new logistics systems, to enhance the traceability and authenticity of raw materials along the F&V value chain. Commercial feasibility will be assessed, including consumer acceptance and regulatory, safety and environmental aspects.

Keywords

non-thermal processing
EU project
fruit and vegetable value chains

S04.2 Mobile solutions for fruit and vegetables producers

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Abstract

FOX – Food processing in a Box – is aiming to transform innovative large-scale technologies for the processing of fruits and vegetables, to small, flexible and mobile container units to demonstrate these innovations in regional hubs. Mild processing technologies are researched for their possibilities for fruit and vegetable processing on small scale, focusing on processing conditions, impact on product quality, shelf life and safety and integration along the production chain. Minimising the use of resources and packaging material are key. The viability of small-scale applications is investigated (e.g. processing efficiency of smaller batches, smaller flow rates) and possibilities for flexible applications in different regions and for a range of products.

We will present some highlights of the developments related to technology and applications towards fruit and vegetable processing that are currently researched in FOX:

- Development of a mobile unit for low oxygen extracting and preservation of fruit- and vegetable juices using innovative technologies. This small-scale unit will enable high-quality fruit juices and puree production, flexible production for different types of fruits and practical and simple installation and operation on farms.
- Soft fruits, vegetables and mushrooms often cannot be served as ready to eat food. Drying of fruits and vegetables can be a valuable alternative for farmers when the economic situation is not favorable for direct sale of the fresh products. We investigate possibilities for innovative pre-treatments for mild drying and will show the results of the effects of high pressure processing, pulsed-electric field processing and ultrasound on apple drying.
- Strategies for upscaling side-streams of fruit and vegetable to optimise vegetable-based food side streams, create high-quality food products and ingredients via mild processing technologies and develop pre-processing technologies for side streams.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817683.

Keywords

Mild processing
Fruits and vegetables
Mobile solutions
Product quality

S04.3 Sustainable futures in the food sector - a methodological combination of future scenarios and LCA

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Abstract

In the context of the FOX project, we have developed detailed, consistent and pointed “pictures of the future”. The focus was on alternative developments for the food sector along its entire value chain, from production and processing to packaging and logistics as far as sales and consumption. The scenario method applied here, enables a structured examination of conceivable alternative development paths. The three scenarios shed light on different options and promote an understanding of what lies ahead.

The life cycle assessment, however, is based on quantitative data as well as values and numbers related to the present, e.g. alternative options of products (studies unit versus reference unit). In this contribution, a concept to combine future scenarios with a life cycle assessment will be shown. Scenarios of the future European food sector serve as a basis to test the conceptual framework of quantifying the qualitative descriptions and their subsequent combination with LCA.

Keywords

Foresight
LCA
Food System
Scenarios

S04.4 Application of non-thermal processing to minimally processed F&V based products

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Abstract

The aim of the work was to assess and develop an optimal combination of non-thermal sanitization, preservation and stabilization methods to improve the safety while preserving the nutritional quality (up to 30%) and prolonging the shelf-life (up to 50%) of minimally processed F&V products. Two business cases have been studied: (i) minimally processed fruits and vegetables and (ii) fruit and vegetable-based juices & smoothies. Ultrasound (US), electrolysed water (EW), plasma activated water (PAW), high Intensity Pulsed Light and blue Light has been studied for sanitization during washing. Bioactive coatings were applied for quality preservation and shelf-life extension of minimally processed F&V. US and high-pressure processing

(HPP) has been studied to stabilize F&V-based juices & smoothies. Results showed that the plasma activated water has an activation effect when reactive species are combined at low pH. Antimicrobial effect can be obtained after 2 minutes of contact with no effect on nutritional and sensory properties of the food. For US, buoyant of the product was a limitation for the efficacy of the sanitization. Moreover, some of the commodity investigated cannot be properly sanitized, like spinach, lettuce and fennel. On the other hand, promising results were obtained for cherry tomatoes and pear. Same results for EW regarding the typology of product. So cherry tomatoes and pear showed the best results and no effect on nutritional and sensory parameters were observed. Two different bioactive coatings were developed. One with antimicrobial activity and the second one with antioxidant activity. The antioxidant coating was able to extend the pear shelf life of 50%. Main benefits of the application of US and HPP to juices and smoothies are the decimal log reduction of the main target microorganisms and the preservation of the nutritional quality. However, browning can be a critical aspect that need to be controlled.

Keywords

mild technology
food preservation
food quality
shelf life

S04.5 Consumer- and Business- led Innovation in agro-food SMEs

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Abstract

The SHEALTHY project aims to assess and develop an optimal combination of non-thermal sanitization, preservation and stabilization methods to improve the safety, while preserving the nutritional quality and prolonging the shelf-life of mildly processed fruit and vegetables (F&V) products. By combining and modulating non-thermal technologies, the project seeks to respond to consumers' demand for fresh, healthy, convenient, sustainable and locally produced and additive-free food. To make innovation happens, consumers' insight and business models are critical elements. Results of consumers' analysis performed in SHEALTHY show that innovative food processing technologies are not in the top of mind of European consumers. Lack of basic knowledge and trust among consumers was identified as the major potential impediment to their acceptance of F&V products, as consumers reportedly have difficulties in assessing relevant benefits and risks associated with MTs. This merged with the wide analysis of local and regional SMEs needs and expectations leads to the design of new business models tailored to consumer's expectations and SMEs needs. In SHEALTHY project the BMs (and thus related objectives, resources, capabilities) enables the SMEs to create value with partners and appropriate share of the value among key actors along the company value chain, promoting the cooperation between farmers and farmers with producers. These collaborative BMs can act as crucial learning models for SMEs to improve their behaviour and culture towards the market (market orientation), their internal activities organized around the innovative treatment and their relationship with suppliers. Due to shortage in resources and in-house skills (e.g. conducting market research, long term planning and the reluctance in taking risky behaviours), this results in an extremely difficult task for SMEs. In SHEALTHY, , SME-led sustainable holistic, inclusive and collaborative business models is expected to smoothen the adoption of these methods.

Keywords

consumers
business models
agro-food
food processing technologies